

THE INFLUENCE OF PUBLIC PROCUREMENT ON EU PROJECTS AIMED AT COMBATING THE COVID-19 CRISIS

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Abstract

Purpose – This paper aims to investigate how EU grants awarded to increase the capacity to manage the covid-19 health crisis are influenced by the duration of public procurement processes.

Methodology/approach – Empirical study of the public procurement processes carried out within the projects financed by the Large Infrastructure Operational Program - Axis 9 (LIOP 9.1)

Findings – A critical picture of the impact of the duration of the procurement processes carried out within the projects financed from the LIOP 9.1 program on the objectives pursued by this program.

Research limitations/implications – This study does not analyze the ongoing projects nor the particular arguments, motivations or decisions adopted within the public procurement procedures organized by each beneficiary of the Axis 9 POIM program

Practical implications – The results of the study provide information on the specific factors of public procurement processes that can influence the achievement of the objectives of a financing program aimed at eliminating the effects of the COVID 19 crisis.

Originality/value – His paper provides a documented picture of how public procurement processes impacts the objectives of a targeted financing program dedicated to eliminating the effects of a crisis.

Key words: Public procurement, EU Funding, Covid-19 crisis.

Introduction

The problems of public procurement in Romania is well known both from the information circulated in the public space and from the periodic reports carried out by National Agency for Public Procurement (NAPP), the most frequent criticisms being those regarding the very long durations of public procurement processes.

The frequent amendments to the specific legislation only imposed (as an obligation) the reduction of the deadlines for the execution of a public procurement procedure, without analyzing which of the stages of the public procurement process produces the greatest delays.

With the onset of the COVID 19 crisis, public authorities in the EU were put in a position to procure products and services necessary to combat the effects generated by the pandemic, on which occasion they had to carry out public procurement in a crisis context.

As established by Decree no. 195 of 16.03.2020 (The President of Romania, 2020), during the period of action of the state of emergency (15.13.2020-15.05.2020) the contracted authorities had the opportunity to carry out emergency procurement processes, which involved fewer formalities and reduced times.

With the end of the state of emergency (15.05.2020), they had to return to the application of usual public procurement processes, even for the purchase of products aimed to combat the effects of the COVID 19 pandemic, effects that provided health authorities with challenges until the first quarter of 2022.

After Romania's exit from the state of emergency caused by the COVID-19 pandemic, the Ministry of European Funds (MEF) initiated the call for projects. "Strengthening the capacity of the public medical

system to manage the emergency situation caused by the Covid-19 crisis" within Priority Axis 9 Protecting the health of the population in the context of the pandemic caused by COVID-19, Specific Objective 9.1 Increasing the capacity to manage the health crisis COVID- 19. from the Large Infrastructure Operational Program (LIOP 9.1).

LIOP 9.1 projects are mainly aimed at equipping the beneficiaries with medical equipment and devices as well as other specialized products, necessary for the activities to combat the effects of COVID 19.

Therefore, the activities proposed by the LIOP 9.1 projects followed the purchase of products and equipment intended to achieve the following result: „Timely and efficient response of the public medical system to the COVID-19 crisis" (Ministry of European Funds, 2020, pp. 5, 29).

Application guide for LIOP 9.1 approved by MEF Order no. 613/15.05.2020 (Ministry of European Funds, 2020) established an initial calendar for the submission of projects 15.05.30.09.2020, with a deadline for completing the projects 31.12.2020, the budget allocated to these projects being approx. 350 million Euros, 100 percent non-refundable funds secured from the state budget and the budget of the EU.

LIOP 9.1 projects were implemented according to the framework specific to projects financed by EU funds and the object and activities proposed by these projects were similar. In the same way, the ongoing procurements within these projects were mostly similar in terms of the object and type of procurements. These elements provided a unitary and comparable framework, favorable for the conduct of our research

Through this measure, a number of 159 projects were contracted, amounting to a contracted value of funding of approx. 168 million euros.

Because of the slow development of these projects, the MEF adopted repeated decisions to extend the project implementation period until 30.04.2021¹, until 18.06.2021², until 31.08.2021³ respectively until date of 31.12.2023⁴.

Analyzing this preliminary picture, we naturally raised the following question: "Are the public procurement processes carried out at the level of the beneficiaries of this financing adapted to a quick response to eliminate crisis situations?"

Theoretical model and methodology

Theoretical model

The public procurement process consumes both material and time resources, directly affecting the activities proposed within the projects with non-reimbursable EU funding.

Analyses and reports carried out at the national level have repeatedly contrasted the fact that often delays in the activities of contracting authorities are mainly due to cumbersome public procurement processes.

The latest NAPP report for the year 2020 on "Indicators for monitoring the efficiency of public procurement procedures" (Național Agency for Public Procurement, 2020) indicates that the average time of public procurement procedures carried out in Romania, related to supply contracts, is 70 days, of which the average time for evaluation of offers is 50 days.

Analyzing from the perspective of the implementation duration of LIOP 9.1 projects, repeatedly extended, the following natural question emerged: How does the durations of public carried out within a LIOP 9.1 project influence the implementation duration of these projects?

In order to identify a substantiated answer to this question, an in-depth study of the elements and how they impact the public procurement process on the calendar of the projects within which they take place was necessary.

¹ thru MEF Order no. 807/07.07.2020

² thru MEF Order no. 1364/18.11.2020

³ thru MEF Order no. 597/10.06.2021

⁴ thru MEF Order no. 904/30.08.2021

Within this research, the processes that take place within these projects were structured as follows:

- a) Activities assigned to the beneficiary regarding the public procurement processes within the project, which were structured in the following relevant stages:
 - i. Stage of the preparation of procedure
 - ii. Stage of bid submission
 - iii. Stage of the offer evaluation
- b) Activities assigned to the supplier, respectively the period of performance of the supply activities that are the subject of the public procurement contracts signed within the project.

Practically, the two sets of specific activities presented above determine the total project implementation period.

The activities presented above can be extended by a series of external events, which are not directly generated by the contracting authority and which can bring significant delays in the calendar of the public procurement process/projects, such as: (1) the introduction of an appeal by a bidder, (2) the selection of the procedure in the ex-ante control program run by the NAPP or even (2) the cancellation of the procedure.

Therefore it is relevant to understand how the occurrence of such events affects the calendar related to a public procurement process.

In this context, the final form of the research question takes the following shape: How do the stages of public procurement, respectively the external factors, influence the total duration of the implementation of the project in which the procurement takes place?

Methodology

To directly answer the research question, we selected the case study as the appropriate method for analyzing the results and how the stages/events influenced the implementation duration of a LIOP 9.1 project.

The collected data comes from the SEAP public procurement platform as well as from the documents and reports issued by the MEF (as the body responsible for the implementation of these financings) regarding the implementation of the LIOP 9.1 projects.

From these projects, for this research, only the projects that were in the completed stage on 31.05.2022, respectively 40 projects, were selected as units of analysis. This selection accumulates a total value of 98.7 million euros, representing 34% of the total number of financed projects, respectively 58.70% of the total value of the financed projects, a share considered significant and relevant for the research results.

From the report published on the website of the MEF (Annex 3 List of contracted projects 31.05.2022⁵), only the LIOP 9.1 projects were selected (according to the "Priority Axis/Investment priority" selector) which were in the „finished" stage (according to the "Project status").

For each of the 40 selected projects, data related to the public procurement procedures carried out within these projects were extracted from the SEAP platform, namely: (1) the unique number of the procedure, respectively the unique code of the related project, (2) the publication date of the procedure, (3) the deadline for submission of offers, (4) the date of deliberation (the date of completion of the evaluation of offers), (5) information regarding the appeals submitted, the progress of the ex-ante NAAP control or the cancellation of the procedure.

These data have been supplemented with the relevant information obtained from the MEF report (Ministry of European Funds, 2022) such as: (1) date of project initiation, (2) date of completion of project activities.

For the identification and extraction of data related to procurement procedures from SEAP and those related to LIOP 9.1 project, both the name of the beneficiary and the SMIS code (unique project identification code) were used as identification keys related to public procurement procedures/projects, keys that can be found in both the MEF report and the SEAP.

⁵ <https://mfe.gov.ro/wp-content/uploads/2022/06/b6a32eb035c5643fc9c3a9245e5f5d05.xlsx>

Research Design

Research variable

This study is aimed at identifying the way in which public procurement processes influence the calendar of LIOP 9.1 projects.

In this sense, it was analyzed:

- ✓ how events external to public procurement processes influenced the stages of public procurement processes, the total duration of public procurement process and the total duration of the projects
- ✓ the way in which the stages of public procurement influenced the total calendar of public procurement processes
- ✓ the way in which the total calendar of public procurement processes influenced the total calendar of projects

The variables used in this paper are based on the stages/elements selected and defined in accordance with the methodologies for the organization and application of public procurement procedures, imposed by law no. 98 from 2016 on public procurement

The specific details of each variable are described below.

Stages of the public procurement process (S)

The stages of the public procurement process consist of three relevant variables:

- ✓ Stage of procedure preparation (S1)
- ✓ Stage of bid submission (S2)
- ✓ Stage of bid evaluation (S3)

S1 - The stage of procedure preparation - refers to the period necessary to define the need and needs to be satisfied by the public procurement contract, drafting and approving the procurement documents describing these elements. In LIOP 9.1 projects, the preparation stage of the procedure begins with the initiation of the project and ends with the publication in SEAP of the procurement notice together with the procurement documents. The study of this stage is relevant from the point of view of evaluating the time required by the contracting authority to prepare the procurement documents and obtain their related approvals.

S2- The stage of bid submission refers to the period between the date of publication of the procurement notice in SEAP and the bid submission deadline. In LIOP 9.1 projects, this stage must be proportionally correlated with the type and object of the organized procedure. The study of this stage is relevant from the perspective of evaluating the time required for bidders to prepare and submit bids.

S3- The stage of bid evaluation refers to the period between the moment of submission of tenders and the moment of deliberation and selection of the winning tenderer (according to SEAP data) and exclusively involves the activity of the bid evaluation commission for the evaluation of all offers submitted in a tender. The study of this stage is relevant from the point of view of the evaluation of the time and professional resources necessary to be involved by the contracting authority for the in-time completion of the bid evaluation process.

External factors (F)

The relevant external factors that extend the calendar of public procurement and the projects in which they take place are represented by the following variables:

- ✓ Appeal (F1)
- ✓ Ex-ante Control (F2)
- ✓ Cancellation of the procedure (F3)

F1- The appeal refers to the action of a bidder to file an appeal at the National Council for Solving Complaints (NCSC) level or a complaint in court if the decisions taken by the purchaser harm its legitimate interests. This process is carried out according to law 101 from 2016, and leads to significant delays in the calendar related to the public procurement process, determined by the specific times of the appeal/complaint resolution process at the NCSC/court level. The study of this factor is relevant through the lens of evaluating how appeals influence the implementation calendar of LIOP 9.1 projects.

F2 - Ex-ante control refers to the function of exercising ex-ante control by the NAPP, according to Emergency Ordinance no. 98 of 2017. This control requires additional time (of an administrative nature) necessary for the consultation and/or approval by NAPP observers of all papers and decisions adopted during the procedure (The Government of Romania, 2017). The study of this factor is relevant from the perspective of evaluating the way in which this control influences the implementation calendar of LIOP 9.1 projects.

F3- Cancellation of the procedure refers to the situation when the contracting authority is obliged to cancel a procurement procedure, according to Law 98 of 2016 on public procurement. The most common situations for which a procedure is canceled are determined (mainly) by the lack of response offers or serious errors done by the purchaser that irreversibly lead to the violation of the law (The Romanian Parliament, 2016). The study of this factor is relevant in terms of evaluating how the cancellation of public procurement procedures influences the implementation calendar of LIOP 9.1 projects.

Duration of the public procurement process (D)

The duration of the public procurement process refers to the period between the initiation of project activities and the moment of deliberation and selection of the winning bidder and includes all the activities and stages specific to public procurement imposed by the applicable legal framework for the contracting authority to be fulfilled. In other words, the duration of the public procurement process consists of all three stages described above (3.1.1). Studying the duration of the public procurement process is relevant from the perspective of evaluating its weight in the total time budget allocated to the project's activities.

Project implementation duration (P)

The duration of project implementation refers to the period between the initiation of project activities and the completion of project implementation. Practically, in the case of the projects selected in this research, due to the specifics of the activities defined within them, the difference between the duration of the project implementation and the duration of the public procurement process is the duration of the executing of the public procurement contracts within the project. Studying the duration of project implementation is relevant in terms of evaluating how it is influenced by the other factors above

Influences studied

In relation to the procurement processes provided by the public procurement legislation, in order to achieve the objectives of the research, the influences that were studied were structured in five groups, presented in table no. 1.

Table no.1

<i>Influences 1 (I-1)</i>	The influence of external factors (F1, F2, F3) on the stages of the public procurement processes (S1, S2, S3)
<i>Influences 2 (I-2)</i>	The influence of external factors (F1, F2, F3) on the total duration of the public procurement processes (D)
<i>Influences 3 (I-3)</i>	The influence of external factors (F1, F2, F3) on the total duration of project implementation (P)
<i>Influences 4 (I-4)</i>	The influence of the stages of the public procurement process (S1, S2, S3) on the total duration of the public procurement processes (D)
<i>Influences 5 (I-5)</i>	The influence of the total duration of the public procurement processes carried out within a project (D) on the total duration of project implementation (P)

Research model

The research model used (see fig. 1) is inspired by the NAPP Public Procurement Guide (National Agency for Public Procurement, 2022) in correlation with the legal provisions on public procurement (The Romanian Parliament, 2016).

Fig. 1. Research model

Data analysis

Factor analysis

The data collected online from the MEF report and SEAP, valid on May 31, 2022, reveal that, within the 40 selected LIOP 9.1 projects, a number of 109 public procurement procedures took place, which constituted the sample of study.

For the selected public procurement procedures, the durations of the stages of the public procurement process (S1-S3) were determined and examined, analyzing distinctly the procedures that were affected by external factors (F1-F3), the results being shown in table no. 2.

Table no. 2

<i>External factors (F)</i>	<i>No. of affected procedures</i>	<i>Incidence rate (%)</i>
<i>F1</i>	18	16,51%
<i>F2</i>	3	2,85%
<i>F3</i>	12	11,01%

The average duration of public procurement processes (D) was 343 days, representing 86% of the average duration of the projects (P) within these procurements took place (398 days).

Table no. 3

	Average total sample duration (days)	Average duration affected by F1		Average duration affected by F2		Average duration affected by F3	
		days	% variation	days	% variation	days	% variation
S1	254	N/A ⁶		159	-37,4%	N/A ⁷	
S2	28	37	+32,14%	45	+60,7%		
S3	60	56	-6,6%	132	+120%		
D	343	322	-6,1%	336	-2,0%		
P	398	439	+10,3%	397	0%	450	+13,1%

⁶ The appeal (F1) is introducing in stages S2 or S3, and have no relevance in relation to S1.

⁷ Canceling a procedure (F3) leads to the cancellation of all stages of the procedure and has no relevance in relation to S1-S3.

The average values for each stage of public procurement (S1-S3) were compared with the average duration of public procurement processes (D) and with the average duration of the projects within these procedures took place (P).

The impact of factors F1 and F2 on the duration of S1-S3, D and P related to public procurement procedures in relation to the average of all selected procedures/projects are shown in table no. 3.

Influences relieved

The results of the exploratory study revealed the following influences:

Influences I-1:

The F1 factor had an influence on S2 (+34.14 percent) and on S3 (-6,6 percent);

The F2 factor had an influence on S1 (-37,4 percent), on S2 (+60,7 percent) and on S3 (+120%).

Influences I-2:

D was influenced by factor F1 (-6,1 percent) and F2 (-2 percent).

Influences I-3:

P was influenced by factor F (+10,3 percent) and by factor F2 (+13,1 percent). F2 factor had no an influence on P.

Influences I-4:

D has been influenced by S1 (having a weight in it of 74 percent), by S2 (having a weight in it of 8 percent) and by S3 (having a weight in it of 18 percent)

Influences I-5:

D has influence on P, having a weight in it of 86 percent.

Discussions

The results show that the average preparation time of a public procurement procedure consumed approx. 3/4 of the time resources allocated to the public procurement processes carried out within the LIOP 9.1 projects (see fig. 2).

The other stages (S2, S3) had comparative values with the national averages, for the procedures for awarding supply contracts, respectively 20 days for S2 and 50 days for S3 (Național Agency for Public Procurement, 2020, p. 47).

Figure 2

In the same way, the time budget of a LIOP 9.1 project was largely allocated to public procurement processes (86 percent) and less the execution processes of the supply contracts signed within these projects (see fig. 3)

The appeals (F1) led to the extension of only the tendering stage (S2), with the tender evaluation stage S3 being shorter by 6.6%. This influence, however, did not lead to the extension of the duration of the D procurement processes, but it extended the total duration of the P projects.

This situation is explained by the fact that a number of three contested procedures were also affected by the F3 factor that determined the cancellation of the procedure, the average P for them being much higher than the average of the sample (475 days)

The ex-ante controls (F2) determined both the extension of the bid submission stage (E2) and the bid evaluation stage (E3). This is happened due to the additional bureaucratic processes imposed by the control exercised by the NAPP.

Figure 3.

On the contrary, due to the methodology applied on the process of drawing up the procedure documents, the NAPP control (F2) determined a significant decrease in the preparation stage of the procedure (E1), a fact which, through the weight held by it, determined a decrease in the duration of the entire procurement process by -2% and a zero impact on the total duration of the project (P).

In the same way, the appeals (F1) and the cancellation of the procedures (F3) had a negative impact on the total durations of the implementation of the projects P, according to fig. 4. The ex-ante control (F2) had no influences of the total duration of the projects.

Figure 4.

Conclusions

Synthesis of research results

In response to the research question, we consider that the duration of the POIM 9.1 projects circumscribed to our study was majorly affected by the stage of preparation of procedure.

The fact that the average duration between the initiation of the projects and the completion of the procurement within the projects was almost an year (343 days), we consider that the "Timely and efficient response of the public medical system to the COVID-19 crisis" pursued by the financier through the financing of the LIOP 9.1 was delayed mainly by the activities allocated for preparing the procurement documents.

These explain mostly the reasons why the implementation period of these projects, which contribute to the speedy removal of the effects of a health crisis, was extended until the end of 2023, probably beyond the horizon in which this crisis will produce effects that require the procured products.

The impact of appeals and Ex-ante NAPP controls on public procurement procedures circumscribed our study had added further delays on project implementation periods by max. 52 days (max. 13%).

It is clear that without intervening on the elements that led to the negative influence of the calendar of the projects analyzed, the future financing measures that aim to remove the effects of some crises will suffer in the same way as those in our study.

Contributions of the study

This study relieved how each stage of the procedure and each factor negatively influenced the total durations of the public procurement processes as well as the total durations of the implementation of LIOP 9.1 projects sampled.

The research model chosen and the influences studied within the research allowed the identification, collection and processing of data through direct comparative analyses.

The results of the study provide both theoretical and empirical results regarding how the implementation of EU-funded projects are affected by the public procurement processes carried out within them.

From an academic perspective, this paper adds more knowledge on how the stages of public procurement processes and the external factors that influence them are connected with the calendar of the projects within which they take place.

Managerial implications of the research

From a practical perspective, the study provides a useful picture for decision-makers involved in project management, respectively suggesting to them an appropriate prioritization of time resources and adequate risk management.

At the same time, the results of the research help the responsible authorities to identify concrete ways to reduce the preparation times of the awarding procedures taking place within the framework of EU projects.

Another advantage offered is the fact that this research offers the people involved in the design and implementation of EU projects a starting point in their own analyzes and evaluations regarding the planning and running of the activities within these projects.

Research limits and future research directions

The research did not fully cover all 159 LIOP 9.1 projects. At the time of this work 119 LIOP 9.1 projects are still in the course of implementation, respectively the public procurement portfolios within them are in various stages of development, a fact that did not allow us to find out what are the delays recorded in these procurement portfolios.

At the same time, the team could not identify the specific causes that caused the delays in the preparation stage of the award procedures, nor the specific reasons that led to the submission of appeals or the cancellation of the procedures.

Because this research aimed only on projects that were financed through LIOP 9.1, we intend to continue the research also at the level of other financing programs as well as other types of purchases (services or works).

Last but not least, the data collected thru the research made us to believe that in-depth research is needed regarding the concrete measures that can be adopted within specific financing measures, to reduce the deadlines for public procurement, such as the establishment of standardized bid documentation or the development of procurement guidelines specific to certain types of EU financing/projects.

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